

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES OF PARTNERSHIP IN DESIGN EDUCATION BETWEEN ZAPORIZHZHIA NATIONAL UNIVERSITY AND BALTIC INTERNATIONAL ACADEMY

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Abstract. The collaboration between Zaporizhzhia National University and the Baltic International Academy in the field of design education has fostered an exchange of expertise and strengthened partnerships in both scientific and educational domains. The signing of a memorandum of understanding in 2020 paved the way for joint initiatives, including educational and cultural events, as well as collaborative scientific and educational projects. The internships and exchange programs involving Mihail Kopeikin and the Department of Design at Zaporizhzhia National University have not only enriched the learning experience for students but also identified key areas for future collaboration, emphasizing the importance of international dialogue in shaping highly skilled and socially responsible design professionals.

Keywords: Design education, Graphic design, High education, Euro Integration, Internationalization.

The international activities of institutions providing design education are aimed at integrating educational services and scientific potential into the international design community, providing additional opportunities for comprehensive development. In 2020, a memorandum of understanding and cooperation was signed with the Baltic International Academy (Baltijas Starptautiskā Akadēmija, Latvia, Riga) and Zaporizhzhia National University, outlining prospective areas of collaboration, including educational, scientific, and cultural events, as well as the development and implementation of joint scientific and educational projects.

Recognizing the importance of research and the significant achievements of Ukrainian and Latvian scientists, a cooperation agreement in the field of research was

signed to enhance the effectiveness of international collaboration among educational institutions.

The Baltic International Academy is the largest non-governmental institution of higher education in the Baltic and Northern European countries (established in 1992), with approximately 2057 students, including over 500 international students from 30 countries in Europe and beyond. The School of Design at the Baltic International Academy is one of the most influential centers for European design education, led by Kopeikin Mihail – an organizer and participant in numerous international workshops and scientific conferences, as well as international academic mobility programs, where he conducted guest lectures and workshops. Since 1998, the Baltic International Academy has actively developed Baltic design education, and in 2003, it launched the School of Design with three levels of education (college, bachelor's, master's). The design programs consistently received the highest ratings from the Ministry of Education of Latvia during regular licensing and accreditation evaluations. In recognition of this, Kopeikin Mihail was awarded letters of appreciation from the Ministry of Education of Latvia in 2007. The educational process includes professional practices, some financed by EU funds, during which students apply their acquired knowledge and skills in practical settings. Mentors of global caliber, an open culture, and opportunities to influence the present are integral to the learning experience. Interns work one-on-one with mentors, receive support from managers, and have access to the entire staff community for success. The administration of the School of Design at the Baltic International Academy creates a cultural program beyond work with events, community engagement, and networking events with academy staff. The quality of education is guaranteed by an accredited curriculum, a dynamically and rationally developing infrastructure (the academy has 12 computer labs, 17 reading rooms, the «BIART» art gallery, a drawing and ceramics studio, the Rerikh Hall, and a unique «Media-Mist» system: Riga, Daugavpils, Ekabpils, Rezekne, Liepaja, Ventspils), and highly qualified teaching staff with extensive experience in the field of design. During their studies, students at the School of Design primarily work on computers using various graphic editors popular in the job market (vector, raster, animation, 3D, etc.) (Digital Visualization Design, 2023).

The Department of Design at Zaporizhzhia National University is one of the leading educational and research centers and a powerful hub for design education in northern Ukraine. The department is headed by Hanna Chemerys, a Ph.D. in pedagogy, associate professor, and a member of the Ukrainian Designers' Association, with a substantial number of scientific publications in the field of design. The teaching staff at the department consists of highly qualified researchers and educators who are members of professional creative associations, including the Ukrainian Designers' Association, the National Union of Artists of Ukraine, and the Ukrainian Advertising Association. The department actively collaborates with leading design studios and agencies in Zaporizhzhia and Ukraine, providing students with practical skills and experience in the field of design. Additionally, the

department organizes various competitions and events aimed at promoting design and developing students' creative abilities. The Department of Design at ZNU is an active participant in the international educational space, cooperating with universities and educational institutions in other countries, including Poland, Germany, France, and the USA. The department is also actively involved in the cultural life of Zaporizhzhia, organizing exhibitions, competitions, workshops, and other events to popularize design.

As part of the collaboration between institutions, Mihail Kopeikin was involved in teaching master's students in the educational-professional program «Graphic Design» with a focus on the discipline «Digital Design.» This involvement aimed to expose students to the experience of design research, project innovations, and the exploration of digital design technologies across various life domains. The educational and research activities provided an opportunity to discuss various issues related to digital design, highlighting interesting topics in 3D visualization, corporate styling, advertising for various companies, and the creation of user interface designs for websites.

As part of the international internship program, there were discussion platforms and practical sessions in the form of case studies. Experience was exchanged regarding the peculiarities of organizing and implementing innovative teaching technologies in institutions. Within the internship, the hosting party provided an opportunity to attend an exhibition of diploma and coursework projects and participate in master classes led by leading instructors from the School of Design. Additionally, an overview of the teaching methodology for fundamental disciplines in «Graphic Design,» such as «Painting,» «Drawing,» «Composition,» «Typography,» «Coloristics,» and «Computer Graphics,» was conducted. Specialized disciplines aimed at mastering a wide range of design directions, including user interface (UI/UX) design and modeling scenarios for virtual and material (including 3D) environments, animation/video, and simulation processes were also explored. The scientific and organizational events of the internship were fruitful, as they identified key directions for collaboration with Baltic colleagues in jointly implementing scientific programs and research, expanding opportunities for student credit mobility, and teaching students through exchange programs.

The internship concluded with the understanding that inter-university dialogue is important and necessary for preparing professionals in the field of design, conducting further joint scientific research, and facilitating student exchanges. In the educational cooperation direction, plans include conducting bilateral distance events to exchange experience in teaching methodology and professional activities, as well as organizing joint scientific and methodological seminars, conferences, professional sessions, and lectures. Involving highly qualified foreign design experts will provide an opportunity to educate internationally competent and socially responsible professionals.

References:

1. Department of Design (2023). ZNU. URL:
<https://www.znu.edu.ua/ukr/university/departments/spp/Departaments/12651>
2. Digital Visualization Design (2023). BSA. URL:
<https://bsa.edu.lv/index.php/en/bachelor-study-programmes/computer-design.html>